

1,2,3,4-Thiatriazoles: Synthesis of 5-Benzylamino, 5-Benzylthio and 5-Benzyloxo-1,2,3,4-Thiatriazoles

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5-Benzylamino-, 5-benzylthio- and 5-benzyloxo-1, 2, 3, 4-thiatriazoles have been synthesized from the corresponding thiosemicarbazides, dithiocarbazates and xanthogen hydrazides respectively. Their IR and UV spectra were studied.

Chemistry of 1,2,3,4-thiatriazoles has been excellently reviewed by Jensen and Pedersen¹.

Present authors have synthesized a series of 5-substituted 1,2,3,4-thiatriazoles in such a way that the benzyl group has been attached to the thiatriazole ring system through various isosters such as -NH-, S- and -O- so that the effect of isosterism on the stability and spectral properties of these compounds can be evaluated.

For this purpose, a series of benzyl thiosemicarbazides², benzyl dithiocarbazates³ and benzyl xanthogen hydrazides⁴ were synthesized by the standard procedures reported in the literature. These were cyclised by the nitrous acid method⁵ to the corresponding 5-substituted 1, 2, 3, 4-thiatriazoles. Various thiosemicarbazides, dithiocarbazates and xanthogen hydrazides prepared are reported in Tables I, II and III respectively. The thiatriazoles are reported in Table IV.

TABLE I-
4-Substituted Thiosemicarbazides

R	R.NH.CSNHNH ₂	M.P. (°C)	Molecular Formula	Analysis %N		Analysis %S	
				Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
1. C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	(a)	128-9	C ₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	—	—	—	—
2. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	(b)	155-6	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	—	—	—	—
3. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	(b)	176	C ₉ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	—	—	—	—
4. <i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	(b)	157	C ₈ H ₁₀ ClN ₃ S	—	—	—	—
*5. <i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -		155-7	C ₆ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S	24.60	24.78	14.15	14.16
*6. <i>p</i> -CN.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -		150-2	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	27.18	27.18	15.43	15.53
*7. <i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -		191	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	24.90	25.00	14.29	14.29
*8. <i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -		136-7	C ₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ OS	19.90	19.95	15.10	15.11

*New Compounds.

(a) M. Tisler, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 1956, **28** 147-54 C.A., 1957, **51**, 12016.

(b) Pathan and Trivedi, *J. Indian Chem.* 1960, **37** (7), 432, C.A., 1960, **55**, 1501.

All melting points are uncorrected.

1. K. A. Jensen and C. Pedersen, in *Advances in Heterocyclic Chemistry*, vol. 3, pp. 263, Academic Press.
2. K. A. Jensen, U. Anthoni, B. Kagi, C. Larsen and C. Pedersen, *Acta Chim Scand.*, 1968, **22**, 2.
3. L. F. Audrieth, E. Scott and P. Kirpur, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 733.
4. J. Wangel, *Arkiv Kemi*, 1950, **1**, 431; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1950, **44**, 6818.
5. E. Lieber, E. Oftdahl, C. Pillai and R. Hines, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1957, **22**, 441

TABLE II
Substituted Dithiocarbazinates

R	M.P. (°C)	Molecular Formula	Analysis % N		Analysis % S	
			Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
			R. S. CSNHNH ₂			
1. C ₃ H ₉ CH ₂ †	125	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ S ₂	—	—	—	—
*2. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	136	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.11	13.21	30.01	30.19
*3. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	115	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ S ₂	13.25	13.21	30.25	30.19
*4. <i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	106	C ₈ H ₉ ClN ₂ S ₂	12.00	12.04	27.82	27.92
*5. <i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	130	C ₈ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	17.30	17.28	26.43	26.33
*6. <i>p</i> -CN.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	106	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	18.65	18.83	28.85	28.70
*7. <i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	99	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ S ₂	17.22	17.42	26.66	26.55
*8. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	165	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS ₂	12.35	12.28	28.18	28.07

*New Compounds.

†Audrieth, Scott, Kirpur, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1954, **19**, 740.

TABLE III
Substituted Xanthogen Hydrazides

R	M.P. (°C)	Molecular Formula	Analysis % N		Analysis % S	
			Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
			R. O. CSNHNH ₂			
1. C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ †	126	C ₈ H ₁₀ N ₂ OS	—	—	—	—
*2. <i>o</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	45	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	14.18	14.28	16.30	16.32
*3. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	92	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ OS	14.28	14.28	16.42	16.32
*4. <i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	66	C ₈ H ₉ ClN ₂ OS	12.91	12.87	14.71	14.71
*5. <i>p</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	163	C ₈ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.45	18.42	14.00	14.04
*6. <i>p</i> -CN.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	166	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	20.18	20.18	15.30	15.38
*7. <i>p</i> -(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	83	C ₁₀ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS	18.39	18.49	14.17	14.16
*8. <i>p</i> -CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ CH ₂ -	180	C ₉ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	13.31	13.21	15.16	15.10

*New Compounds.

†Jorgon Berger, *Acta. Chem. Scand* 1952, **6**, 1565.

It was observed that these compounds were stable only for few hours at room temperature and for few days at 0°. Some of the compounds in 5-benzylaminoseries were found to explode with a sharp note when heated on a spatula. The relative

TABLE IV
1, 2, 3, 4-Thiatriazoles

R	M.P. (°C)	Molecular Formula	Analysis % N		Analysis % S		
			Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated	
*1. C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	-NH.	80-81	C ₈ H ₈ N ₄ S	29.01	29.16	16.50	16.66
*2. o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	105	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	27.37	27.18	15.64	15.53
*3. p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	180	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ S	27.22	27.18	15.62	15.53
*4. p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	77	C ₈ H ₇ ClN ₄ S	24.58	24.72	14.00	14.13
*5. p-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	45	C ₈ H ₇ N ₅ O ₂ S	29.52	29.54	13.38	13.50
*6. p-CN.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	122	C ₉ H ₇ N ₅ S	32.34	32.25	14.80	14.74
*7. p-(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₃ N ₆ S	29.87	29.78	13.51	13.61
*8. p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-NH.	84-85	C ₉ H ₁₀ N ₄ OS	25.05	25.23	14.20	14.41
*9. C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	-S.	66	C ₉ H ₇ N ₃ S ₂	19.95	20.01	30.50	30.63
*10. o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	105	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	18.74	18.83	28.63	28.70
*11. p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	125	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S ₂	18.90	18.83	28.72	28.70
*12. p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	109	C ₈ H ₆ ClN ₃ S ₂	17.20	17.25	26.30	26.28
*13. p-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	102	C ₈ H ₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	21.90	22.05	25.10	25.20
*14. p-CN.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	110	C ₉ H ₆ N ₄ S ₂	23.89	23.93	27.45	27.35
*15. p-(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	120	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂	22.11	22.22	25.11	25.40
*16. p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-S.	166	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS ₂	17.48	17.57	26.75	26.78
*17. C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	-O.	54	C ₈ H ₇ N ₃ OS	21.67	21.75	16.48	16.58
*18. o-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	115	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	20.18	20.28	15.36	15.46
*19. p-CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	68	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ OS	20.30	20.28	15.50	15.46
*20. p-Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	64	C ₈ H ₆ ClN ₃ OS	18.37	18.46	14.00	14.06
*21. p-NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	170	C ₉ H ₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	23.42	23.51	13.54	13.44
*22. p-CN.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	122	C ₉ H ₆ N ₄ OS	25.70	25.69	14.60	14.66
*23. p-(CH ₃) ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	142	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ N ₄ OS	23.62	23.73	13.68	13.56
*24. p-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ -	-O.	172	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ O ₂ S	18.72	18.83	14.25	14.35

*New Compounds.

stabilities of these thiatriazoles were qualitatively observed to be in the following order ;

- (a) $Y = -NH-$ thiosemicarbazides $Y = -NH-$ 5-benzylamino-1, 2, 3, 4-thiatriazole.
 (b) $-S-$ dithiocarbazines $-S-$ 5-benzylthio-1, 2, 3, 4-thiatriazole.
 (c) $-O-$ xanthogenhydrazides $-O-$ 5-benzyl-oxo-1, 2, 3, 4-thiatriazole.

$X = H, o-$ and $p-CH_3, p-Cl, p-NO_2, p-CN, p-(CH_3)_2 N-, p-CH_3O-$

An IR absorption frequencies of these thiatriazoles lead us to assign the region 960-930 cm^{-1} and 1160-1115 cm^{-1} as characteristic absorption for this ring system. Although earlier authors (cf. Ref. 1) have assigned the strong band at 1625-1600 cm^{-1} region to NH_2 deformations, we believe this to be due to $-N=N-$ group. It appears from this study that there seems to be no specific effect of isosterism ($-NH-$, $-O-$ and $-S-$) on the absorption spectra of thiatriazoles studied.

The UV spectra of these thiatriazoles having different isosters also show similarity. The first band shows remarkable similarity in absorption at 220, 225 and 227.5 $m\mu$, while the second band shows slight variations. We conclude that the isosters used as bridge between the thiatriazole ring system show similarity and no effect of isosterism seems to be apparent from the present studies.

Although initially we thought of studying the physiological properties of some of the compounds, due to the unstable nature of the products, we could not pursue this study. Analysis of these thiatriazoles offered special difficulty. All of these have to be analysed within six to eight hours of their preparation. Parr and Oxygen flask methods were used for analysis of sulphur.

EXPERIMENTAL

All melting points are uncorrected.

Synthesis of 1, 2, 3, 4-Thiatriazoles : A mixture of thiosemicarbazide, dithiocarbazine or xanthogen hydrazide (0.1 mole) and 76 ml. of 15% (about 4 N) hydrochloric acid (0.3 mole) was taken in a three-necked flask carrying a stirrer, a dropping funnel and a thermometer. A solution of 6.9 g (0.1 mole) of sodium nitrite in 50 ml of water was gradually added to the vigorously stirred mixture while keeping the temperature at 10-15°. The addition was complete in 30 mins after which the mixture was stirred for another 10 mins. The white powdery material which rapidly turned pale pink, was filtered. This was crystallised either from benzene, methanol or aqueous acetone. Yields were between 50 to 55%.